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EFFECT OF FOOD ADDITIVES ON HUMAN HEALTH

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ПИЩЕВЫХ ДОБАВОК НА ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

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Abstract

Nutrition is one of the most important needs for a person to manage his life. Today, with the increase in the production of manufactured and packaged foods, the use of food additives has become widespread. The purpose of adding these substances to foods is to prevent spoilage of foods, to extend the shelf life, as well as to preserve the qualitative characteristics of the natural color and aroma of foods, and to increase the assortment of foods. Due to the increased consumption of chemicals, we exclude ourselves from natural products when feeding with ready-made meals, which we use without even hesitation due to the small volume, easily edible, but also having an attractive appearance, which leads to an increase in the Daily permissible dose. The aim of this study is to analyze the many effects that protective food supplements have on human health despite being used in predetermined amounts.

Аннотация

Питание-одна из важнейших потребностей человека, чтобы он мог управлять своей жизнью. Сегодня, с увеличением производства полуфабрикатов и расфасованных пищевых продуктов, широкое распространение получило использование пищевых добавок. Целью добавления этих веществ в продукты питания является предотвращение порчи продуктов, продление срока их хранения, а также сохранение качественных характеристик естественного цвета и аромата продуктов и увеличение ассортимента продуктов. Из-за повышенного потребления химикатов, небольшого объема, легко съедобного, а также из-за наличия привлекательного внешнего вида, мы без колебаний отказываемся от натуральных продуктов при кормлении готовыми к употреблению блюдами, что приводит к увеличению суточной допустимой дозы. Цель этого исследования-проанализировать многие эффекты, которые защитные пищевые добавки оказывают на здоровье человека, даже если они используются в заранее определенных количествах.

Keywords: food additives, health, food, pickle, roast

Ключевые слова: пищевые добавки, здоровье, еда, солить, жаркое

Since ancient times, people have developed various methods for keeping food longer without spoiling. They tried to preserve food by salting, vinegar and burnt sulfur. Salt and sugar, the oldest food preservatives, were used to preserve food by reducing water activity to the point where microorganisms could not grow. In the Middle Ages, the purpose of adding nitrate to meat was to prevent botulism (food poisoning). At this time, it was found that he looked healthier and more alive. The Huns have achieved this by using sausages and roasting to preserve meat. The use of food supplements began to increase after the XVIII century. These

substances are used in addition to many products, such as to prevent food from spoiling or to increase its taste and color.

Food additives are chemicals however, substances such as fats, carbohydrates and minerals that are found in foods and are essential for life are also chemical substances. Six hundred twenty-five chemicals were found in coffee, four hundred seventy-five in wine, three hundred twenty-five in bananas, three hundred and fifty in tomatoes, and two hundred and fifty in orange juice [1].

While in the past several thousand natural chemicals were used in all fields, today eighty thousand

chemicals are used for various purposes and this number is increasing. In 1950, the production of chemical substances in the world was seven million tons/year, but now this figure has reached four hundred million tons/year [2].

Depending on the type of food, one or more food additives can be used at the same time. Additives are added to prevent changes in the chemical composition of food, to prevent microbial growth or spoilage.

The rapid development of the food industry has led to an increase in the use of food additives. The properties of food additives and the level of their amounts in the foods in which they are used are investigated and given importance internationally [2].

Although the use of dietary supplements is permitted, they can have toxic effects on the body when consumed continuously and in high amounts [1]. The additives used must have properties that do not affect human health. Each country regulates the foods it can add and the ratio of food additives according to its conditions.

Food additives that enhance the aroma and color of food. Flavoring additives are used to increase the taste or smell of food, to make it more attractive. The most commonly used flavoring agent is monosodium glutamate. It can cause Chinese restaurant syndrome [7]. Ingestion of monosodium glutamate may result in chest pain, facial flushing, flushing, sweating, dizziness, headache, palpitations, nausea, and vomiting. In children, it can be observed with chills and shivering, nervousness, screaming. Apparently 15-20% of the general population is sensitive to small doses of monosodium glutamate. Symptoms begin within an hour of ingestion, but may last up to 14 hours [3]. Colorants are added to food in order to restore the natural color lost during product processing and storage, to give color to colorless food, to strengthen weak color, and to win the favor of the consumer by hiding its poor quality. It is used in many products such as soft drinks, ice creams, candies, powdered drinks, waffles, cookies, creams, chewing gums [7].

The use of food supplements and their impact on health. Despite the benefits of food supplements, consumers are of the opinion that these substances are harmful to health. The reason why the consumer thinks so is the masking of poor-quality or spoiled foods, improper processing of food, preparation of imitated Foods, lowering the nutritional value of the product, using it in excess of the norm to achieve the desired effect, non-observance of processing and packaging techniques [7].

Cancer-causing nitrosamines produce nitrites and nitrates, used as preservatives, which reduce the oxygen-carrying capacity of the blood. Some researchers have begun to investigate methods of reducing nitrite residues and nitrosamine formation in the final product, as meat products produced without nitrites will have a reduced shelf life, tasteless and bad color, thus causing health problems through food poisoning.

Another study tested blue, green, red, yellow and orange food colorings used in baby food. As a result of the study, it was determined that food dyes caused hyperactivity in rats in the first month of birth [5]. The

same researcher suggests that children with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder have significant improvements when artificial colors are removed from their diet. Another piece of evidence that artificial additives cause behavioral problems is that xanthan-type dyes alter the physiological properties of neurons in invertebrates.

In patients with sodiummetabisulfite asthma, asthma attacks cause mutations in thiamine-destroying bacteria. It is added to cookies, waffles, cakes, potato chips and vinegar.

Benzoic acid causes hangovers, skin rashes, migraines. It is added to margarine, olive paste, soft drinks, jam, biscuits, cookies, waffles, cake juices, sauces and ketchups.

It is known that phenolic substances naturally present in the roots of some plants are anticarcinogenic. However, synthetic phenols used as antioxidants also have effects as co-carcinogens, causing precancerous lesions, papillomas, and cancer [6].

The increase in the use of nutritional supplements to increase sales also brings with it many dangers. In countries where there is no necessary control, the allergic, carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects of food additives on human health are not taken into account. The most important factor that food additives will negatively affect human health is the use of these substances in excess of the permissible doses or their non-compliance with the purity of food.

In order to eliminate or minimize the health effects of food supplements, some nuances should be taken into account. When buying a food product, the consumer should pay attention to its shelf life and composition. Goods whose address and quality of production are unknown should not be used because they are on sale at low prices corresponding to the budget. The use of food additives that should be used in production in excess of the recommended amount should be prevented by educating food producers.

It is impossible to completely isolate food supplements from the composition of the foods we use. The important point is to minimize the dangers by ensuring the use of these substances in the way and in quantities established by the laws.

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